

Awake Fiberoptic-Guided Intubation in Difficult Airway: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: The management of the difficult airway remains one of the main challenges in anesthesiology due to the risk of hypoxia, neurological injury, and death associated with inadequate airway control. Awake fiberoptic-guided intubation is a safe and effective strategy in patients with anticipated difficult airway, as it allows securing the airway prior to anesthetic induction while maintaining spontaneous ventilation.

Case Report: We present the case of a 74-year-old female with a history of left breast cancer previously treated with breast-conserving surgery, radiotherapy, and hormone therapy. Six years later, she was scheduled for wide resection of a left shoulder tumor with axillary lymphadenectomy due to basal cell carcinoma associated with metastatic axillary lymph node. During the preanesthetic evaluation, multiple predictors of difficult airway were identified, including short neck with limited cervical extension, 2 cm mouth opening, Mallampati IV classification, and a sternomental distance of 12 cm. Therefore, awake fiberoptic-guided intubation was planned. Supplemental oxygen was administered along with sedation using dexmedetomidine and fentanyl, in addition to nebulization and regional airway block with 2% lidocaine. Intubation was successfully performed using a fiberoptic bronchoscope (LF-2 model) without complications, followed by balanced general anesthesia for the surgical procedure. Intraoperative and immediate postoperative courses were favorable, with no respiratory or hemodynamic adverse events.

Conclusion: Awake fiberoptic-guided intubation is a safe and effective technique in patients with anticipated difficult airway. This case highlights the importance of careful preoperative evaluation, anticipatory planning, and maintaining proficiency in advanced airway management techniques to improve patient safety.

Keywords: Difficult airway, awake intubation, fiberoptic intubation, airway management, anesthesiology, flexible fiberoptic bronchoscope, oncologic surgery, predictors of difficult airway.

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INTRODUCTION

The management of the difficult airway remains one of the main challenges in anesthesiology, as complications derived from inadequate airway control can lead to hypoxia, permanent neurological damage, and even death. Epidemiological studies have estimated that difficult tracheal intubation occurs in approximately 1.9–10% of patients undergoing general anesthesia, while difficulty with face mask ventilation occurs in about 0.66–2.5% of cases.^{1,2} Likewise, the Fourth National Audit Project of the Royal College of Anaesthetists identified that errors in planning and

inappropriate equipment selection are relevant factors in morbidity and mortality associated with airway management.^{1,3}

Awake tracheal intubation is a technique with a high success rate and a favorable safety profile used in patients with anticipated difficult airway. This technique allows securing the airway before the induction of general anesthesia while maintaining spontaneous ventilation and protective airway reflexes, thereby reducing the risk of loss of airway control in anesthetized patients. Although new airway management devices such as videolaryngoscopes and supraglottic devices

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have been developed in recent decades, fiberoptic intubation continues to play a fundamental role in difficult airway management, with reported success rates between 88% and 100%.⁵

Current guidelines recommend considering awake intubation when predictors of difficult airway are present, such as head and neck pathology, history of cervical surgery or radiotherapy, limited mouth opening, reduced cervical mobility, or morbid obesity.^{2,5}

In this context, we present the case of a geriatric patient with predictors of difficult airway undergoing oncologic surgery, in whom awake fiberoptic-guided intubation was performed as a strategy to secure the airway.

CASE REPORT

We present the case of a 74-year-old female patient, originally from and residing in Mérida, Yucatán, a housewife, widowed, and of Catholic religion. As a relevant oncological history, the patient was diagnosed with left breast cancer at clinical stage I, for which she underwent breast-conserving surgery six years prior to the current condition, including sentinel lymph node biopsy and tumor resection of approximately 1.5 cm, without intraoperative complications. Subsequently, she received 12 sessions of radiotherapy and hormonal therapy with anastrozole and tamoxifen, with no record of chemotherapy in her medical file.

Six years after treatment for breast cancer, the patient was referred for preanesthetic evaluation due to basal cell carcinoma of the left shoulder associated with metastatic axillary lymph node, with surgical indication for wide tumor resection of the left shoulder and axillary lymphadenectomy. Regarding symptoms, the medical record did not clearly document subjective complaints such as pain, tumor growth, bleeding, ulceration, functional limitation, or weight loss. However, the need for oncologic surgical treatment was established, along with the presence of predictors of difficult airway, which led to the decision to plan awake fiberoptic-guided intubation. The patient denied cardiovascular and respiratory symptoms.

Non-pathological personal history included being a housewife, widowed, Catholic, and a resident of Mérida. No specific information was reported regarding diet, physical activity, alcohol consumption, smoking, or other lifestyle habits, except that substance use was denied. From a psychosocial standpoint, depression and anxiety under pharmacological treatment were noted. No specific genetic information or family history of breast cancer or other oncological syndromes was documented.

Relevant comorbidities included depression and anxiety treated with sertraline and hydroxyzine; in another note, escitalopram, quetiapine, and chronic use of acetylsalicylic acid for approximately 30 years were also reported. She reported penicillin allergy and denied blood transfusions, asthma, and epilepsy.

Her surgical history included tonsillectomy at age 15 under general balanced anesthesia without known complications; blepharoplasty four years prior under local anesthesia without complications; left breast-conserving surgery with sentinel node biopsy; and curettage for endometrial thickening under subarachnoid block, classified as ASA II without relevant complications.

On preanesthetic physical examination, the patient was conscious and oriented to person but not to time or place. She had a weight of 49 kg and height of 1.40 m, with an approximate body mass index of 25 kg/m². Airway assessment revealed a short neck with limited cervical extension, mouth opening of approximately 2 cm, Mallampati class IV, and sternomental distance of 12 cm, findings consistent with predictors of difficult airway. No mandibular protrusion was observed, and the patient had no teeth or dental prosthesis. She was classified as ASA III.

Prior to the procedure, the anesthetic plan was explained in detail, including awake fiberoptic-guided intubation, and informed consent was obtained. As additional airway preparation, nebulization with lidocaine was performed before regional blocks.

In the operating room, after checking the anesthesia machine, airway management equipment, and suction system, the patient was positioned semi-sitting (semi-Fowler position), and standard monitoring was initiated, including continuous electrocardiography, noninvasive blood pressure, pulse oximetry, and capnography. Initial vital signs were blood pressure 109/55 mmHg, heart rate 72 bpm, respiratory rate 15 rpm, and oxygen saturation 100%.

Given the anticipated difficult airway, awake intubation was performed. Oxygen was administered via nasal cannula at 5 L/min, and sedation was initiated with intravenous dexmedetomidine (total dose 50 mcg) combined with fentanyl 50 mcg. Sedation level was monitored using the Richmond Agitation-Sedation Scale (RASS).

Regional anesthesia of the upper airway was then performed using bilateral superior laryngeal nerve blocks, recurrent laryngeal nerve block, and glossopharyngeal nerve blocks with 2% lidocaine. Adequate tolerance to Yankauer suction was used as a clinical indicator of effective airway anesthesia. Fiberoptic bronchoscopy was then performed using an LF-2 model fiberoptic scope, visualizing a complete glottic ring (Cormack-Lehane II), and a 6.5 mm endotracheal tube was inserted orally. The cuff was inflated with 5 cc of air, and correct placement was confirmed by capnography and bilateral auscultation, securing the tube at 20 cm from the right labial commissure. A videolaryngoscope was also available as a backup device.

Anesthesia was subsequently induced with fentanyl (75 + 75 + 50 mcg IV), lidocaine 200 mg IV, propofol 70 mg IV, and cisatracurium 5 mg IV. Maintenance was achieved with sevoflurane at 2–2.5% and oxygen at 2 L/min, with mechanical ventilation in volume-controlled mode (tidal

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volume 325 ml, respiratory rate 13 rpm, PEEP 5 cmH₂O, maximum pressure 30 cmH₂O).

Additional medications included dexamethasone 8 mg IV, ondansetron 8 mg IV, paracetamol 1 g IV, and atropine 600 mcg IV. Fluid management included 100 ml of 0.9% sodium chloride and 650 ml of Hartmann solution, with total intake of 750 ml, estimated output of 754 ml, and fluid balance of -4 ml. No blood products were administered.

The surgical procedure consisted of wide resection of the left shoulder tumor with axillary lymphadenectomy, without intraoperative complications and minimal bleeding. During anesthesia, the patient remained hemodynamically stable,

with blood pressure 131/79 mmHg, heart rate 91 bpm, respiratory rate 12 rpm, and oxygen saturation 100%.

At the end of the procedure, the surgical site showed no active bleeding. Secretions were aspirated, an oropharyngeal airway was placed, and the patient emerged by metabolic elimination of anesthetic agents. Once clinical criteria were met, extubation was performed without complications. Immediate postoperative evaluation showed an Aldrete score of 9, RASS -2, and pain score (VAS) of 0. The patient had a favorable immediate postoperative course, without respiratory or hemodynamic complications, and no major adverse events were documented.

Figure 1. Patient in preoperative preparation in a semi-sitting position, with a tumor lesion on the left shoulder prior to surgical resection.

Figure 2. Lateral view of the neck during preoperative evaluation, showing features associated with a difficult airway.

DISCUSIÓN

The Fourth National Audit Project (NAP4) evaluated major complications related to airway management during general anesthesia in the United Kingdom, estimating an incidence of approximately 1 serious event per 22,000 anesthetics. Although the overall frequency was low, the analysis showed that in most cases there were deficiencies in planning or in the selection of airway management devices, highlighting the importance of proper preoperative evaluation and anticipatory strategies for difficult airway management.⁶

Recent evidence suggests that fiberoptic intubation remains a fundamental technique for the safe management of anticipated difficult airway, even with the availability of newer technologies such as videolaryngoscopy. For this

reason, it is considered essential that anesthesiologists maintain competence in this technique and use it when clear clinical indications exist. In the present case, the presence of multiple predictors of difficult airway justified the choice of awake fiberoptic-guided intubation as a strategy to safely secure the airway.⁷

Similar to what was described by Khan et al., in our case awake fiberoptic intubation was used as the primary strategy in the presence of predictors of difficult airway, allowing airway control before anesthetic induction. Although indirect rigid devices and videolaryngoscopes have been developed as alternatives to direct laryngoscopy, the flexible bronchoscope remains a fundamental tool in difficult airway management,

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as demonstrated in this case with a successful intubation without complications.⁸

Likewise, Yang et al. described the successful use of awake fiberoptic intubation in patients with ankylosing spondylitis and severe cervical deformity, a condition frequently associated with difficult airway. In their study, intubation was performed under conscious sedation and topical airway anesthesia, allowing maintenance of spontaneous ventilation and safe airway control. These results are comparable to the present case, in which awake fiberoptic-guided intubation, combined with sedation and regional airway blockade, allowed successful intubation without complications in a patient with multiple predictors of difficult airway.⁹

Among the strengths of airway management in this case, the preoperative identification of multiple predictors of difficult airway and the anticipatory planning of a safe airway management strategy using awake fiberoptic-guided intubation stand out. Additionally, the combined use of carefully titrated sedation and regional airway anesthesia allowed maintenance of spontaneous ventilation and improved tolerance of the procedure, reducing the risk of complications associated with anesthetic induction in patients with anticipated difficult airway. Among the limitations of this case is the lack of detailed documentation of some standardized airway assessment parameters in the medical record, such as sternomental distance or neck circumference, which limits a more complete characterization of the expected difficulty.

The available medical literature supports the use of awake fiberoptic intubation as a safe and effective technique in patients with anticipated difficult airway, particularly when anatomical alterations or limitations in cervical mobility are present. In this context, our case reinforces the importance of thorough preoperative evaluation and individualized selection of airway management strategies, considering both patient characteristics and the experience of the anesthesia team.

The main lesson derived from this case is the importance of anticipatory planning in airway management for patients with predictors of difficulty, as well as the need for anesthesiologists to maintain skills in advanced techniques such as awake fiberoptic intubation. Proper patient preparation, adequate topical anesthesia, and carefully titrated sedation can facilitate the safe performance of the procedure and minimize the risk of adverse events.

From the patient's perspective, although no direct testimony regarding her experience during the procedure was obtained, the absence of postoperative complaints, along with a favorable postoperative course without respiratory or hemodynamic complications, suggests that the anesthetic management was well tolerated.

CONCLUSION

Awake fiberoptic-guided intubation represents a safe and effective technique for the management of anticipated

difficult airway. In this case, the preoperative identification of multiple predictors of difficult airway allowed adequate anesthetic planning and airway control prior to anesthetic induction. This case highlights the importance of careful preoperative evaluation and maintaining proficiency in advanced airway management techniques to improve patient safety.

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Conflict of Interest: None

Ethical Considerations: The patient was informed at all times about the diagnosis, the procedures performed, and the potential risks. Written informed consent was obtained for the surgical and anesthetic procedures, as well as for the publication of this case report, in accordance with the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki and the institutional regulations of the hospital.

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